

PENETRATION BEHAVIOR OF ELECTROLYTE SOLUTION THROUGH CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS (CFRTP) MATERIAL USING IN AUTOMOTIVE STRUCTURAL APPLICATION

Patarapon Palungvachira¹, Masatoshi Kubouchi¹, Shinsuke Katayama² and Hiroyuki Ogata²

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Tokyo Institute of Technology,
2-12-1 Ookayama, Mekuro-ku, Tokyo 152-8550, Japan
Email: palungvachira.p.aa@m.titech.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.titech.ac.jp>

²JFE Techno-Research Corporation,
1 Kawasaki-chou, Chuo-ku, Chiba City, Chiba Pref. 260-0835, Japan
Email: s-katayama@jfe-tec.co.jp, web page: <http://www.jfe-tec.co.jp>

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics (CFRTP) are now going to be widely used in a variety of structural application, due to their high specific strength, corrosion resistance and cost performance. Especially in automotive industry, study on CFRTP is being markedly exploited, due to the social demand for developing mass production electric vehicle and ultra-lightweight vehicle. However, when carbon fibers (very efficient cathode) in a polymer based composite are attached to metal parts, degradation such as galvanic corrosion, can occur at an interface between CFRTP and metals. Therefore to prevent the failure of material, it is significantly important to understand how the electrolyte solution penetrates into the CFRTP and cause the galvanic corrosion. In this study, the penetration behavior of water and other electrolytic solution through CFRTP has been investigated. Penetration analysis was examined by measuring mass change and monitoring the penetration depth of chlorine or sulfur element. The degree of degradation was evaluated by flexural property and surface fracture. Measurement of electric conductivity was also conducted to observe change of electrical property. Penetration of water and NaCl solution can be categorized following the Fickian diffusion theory. After drying process, flexural strength returned to almost 100% of initial value in both cases, concluded that there was no chemical reaction occurs by water or NaCl solution. For H₂SO₄ solution penetration behavior, at the initial condition, due to water diffusion, the penetration behavior also follows Fickian's diffusion theory. H⁺ and SO₄²⁻ can penetrates into CFRTP after the degradation of the surface occurs, which will induce a conductivity of CFRTP, and may increase the chance for galvanic corrosion to occur when attached to metals. Lastly, after the surface was fully degraded by H₂SO₄ solution, polymer degradation grows and propagates easily causing the sample to crack and eventually break.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber impart excellent specific strength and stiffness combined with light weight. Due to high strength-to-weight, combined with superior stiffness, has made Carbon fiber the materials choice for high performance composite structures. Therefore, composite materials made of carbon fibers and resins are widely used in a variety of structural application, due to their high specific strength, corrosion resistance [1-3]. In aircraft industry, thermoset-formed carbon fiber composites, known as "Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermosetting Plastic (CFRP)" have already played a huge part in the manufacturing of new airplane [4].

CFRP material has also received much attention for automotive structures because of its high specific stiffness, high specific strength and high damping capability compared to the conventional metallic materials [5-7]. However, thermoset based CFRPs are expensive and the processes used to convert them into production components have been too slow and not suitable for use in high-volume automotive

manufacture. To overcome this disadvantage, a thermoplastic-based carbon fiber composite, so called “Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics (CFRTP)”, has recently been developed and applied. This material can be softened when heat was applied and quickly hardened when it was cooled, all without losing its desirable properties, thus making it ideal for automobile industry. Moreover, due to the social demand for developing mass production electric vehicle, ultra-lightweight vehicle and public concern of environmental problems, study on CFRTP for mass production are being markedly exploited [8]. Also, the global competition to reach trade acceptance, cost reduction and to fulfil the legal requirements of the automobile is among things settled through improved and new materials. A raising of the ecological relief of future vehicle systems has to go along with a distinct lowering of the automobile pollutant emission, for instance CO₂ emission. Especially, automotive engine emissions are recognized as a major source of air pollution [9]. In order to solve this problem, researchers have sought to reduce automotive weight to improve the automotive fuel efficiency. CFRTP application could reduce the weights of structural parts without any reduction of the mechanical performance, which will result in mitigation of the oil consumption and CO₂ emission [7,10].

However, when carbon fibers in a polymer based composite are used as a structural component, it should be noted that carbon fiber is a very efficient cathode and very noble in the galvanic series. Therefore, contact between carbon fiber composites and metals in a corrosive electrolyte (e.g. water, rain, sea water) will cause a variety of degradation such as galvanic corrosion [11]. For example, in automobile, in which exposure to electrolyte such as rain, seawater or battery fluid is inevitable, degradation due to galvanic corrosion has been reported [12]. Especially, if electrolytic solution penetrate through CFRTP and reach the interface between CFRTP and metal, galvanic corrosion will likely to occur. Therefore to prevent this kind of degradation, it is extremely important to understand how the electrolyte solution penetrates into the CFRTP and cause the galvanic corrosion between an interface of CFRTP and metals. In this study, the penetration behaviour of water and other electrolytic solution through CFRTP has been investigated.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Diffusion is the process by which matter is transported from one part of a system to another as a result of random molecular motion. In this study, all samples have lateral dimensions that are greater than their thicknesses; therefore, one-dimensional absorption was assumed during the analyses. The one dimensional absorption behavior can be analyzed in term of Fickian treatment, using the following Fick’s equation. [13-17]:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right] \quad (1)$$

Where, C is the concentration of solution at specific thickness (x) and time (t). The following approach is to deduce the diffusion coefficient from the observation of the overall rate of mass uptake of solution by infinite plane sheet. Such a method has been used to consider the diffusion coefficient of many solutions using the following equation, where the dependence of $M(t)$ with time can be described.

$$\frac{M(t)}{M_{\infty}} = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{8}{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2} \exp \left[\frac{D(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{4L^2} \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

Where, $M(t)$ is the amount of absorbed liquid at time t and M_{∞} is the amount of absorbed liquid at equilibrium. Eq. 2 is the analytical solution of Fick’s second law for the specific case of diffusion through a plane sheet [18]. Simplified solution of eq. 2 showed that for short immersion time, that is $M(t)/M_{\infty} < 0.6$, the following relation can be applied

$$\frac{M(t)}{M_{\infty}} = 4 \left(\frac{Dt}{\pi L^2} \right)^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

The plot of eq.3 should be linear up to $M(t) = 0.6 M_{\infty}$ with less than 2% deviation for true Fickian diffusion. Using this approach, if $M(t)$ is plotted as a function of $t^{0.5}$ the diffusion coefficient can be obtained from the slope of the curve [19,20].

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

3.1 Material

The CFRTP plate were produced by injection molding process. The first primary raw materials for the manufacture of CFRTP plates was PAN-based chopped carbon fibers (HT-606, from TOHO TENAX Co., Ltd), with bulk density of 420 g/dm³ and length of 6 mm. Chopped fiber is carbon fiber with high strength and elastic modulus that is bundled using an optimal sizing agent, and chopped into designated lengths suitable to each application. The second primary raw material was Polyamide 66 resin (AMILAN@CM3001-N, from TORAY Industries Inc.), with tensile strength of 80 MPa and flexural modulus of 2800 MPa at 23 °C.

According to Carbon Fibers and Polyamide mixing ratio, 6 types of CFRTP sample have been produced as shown in Table 1.

Sample No.	PA66 (mass%)	Carbon Fiber (mass%)
1	100	0
2	90	10
3	80	20
4	70	30
5	60	40
6	50	50

Table 1: Content of CFRTP sample.

3.2 Immersion Test

CFRTP plate were cut into size of 25.0 × 60.0 × 3.0 mm³ (Error associated with the measurement of the dimensions was 0.05 mm) using high speed ceramic wheel cutting machine, and then polished with #1200-emery paper. Next step, it was dried in thermo-stated chamber (oven) for at least 100 hours and ensures that its weight reached a stabilized level. At this condition, it was assumed that most of water in sample has been evaporated. Then, the sample were immersed in deionized water, 5 mass% NaCl solution and 5 mass% H₂SO₄ solution at 40°C, 60°C and 80°C as shown in Figure 1. The Temperature is controlled by the Constant temperature water bath (Figure 2). The specimens are periodically taken out for weighing.

Figure 1: Immersion Test.

Figure 2: Constant temperature water bath.

3.3 Penetration analysis

Penetration of solution and degradation of sample was done by observing mass change profile, retention of flexural strength, cross section observation, and measurement of electrical property (electric conductivity).

3.3.1 Mass change measurement

Degradation of CFRTP and penetration of water, NaCl solution and H₂SO₄ solution could be observed from weight change of sample. It showed the amount of solution that penetrated into CFRTP. The

specimens are periodically taken out. Before weighing, the excess surface water is wiped and the specimens are left in air for about 5 min, and weighed using a precision balance. The water gain (M) at a specific immersion time (t) was determined using the following equation (Eq. 4):

$$M(t) = \frac{100(W(t) - W_0)}{W_0} \quad (4)$$

Where, $W(t)$ is the weight of the sample at time t , and W_0 is the weight of the sample before immersion.

3.3.2 Retention of flexural strength

In order to determine the change of mechanical property of CFRTP after specific time of immersion, three points bending test was done on sample, using Instron type machine (AGS 1 KNJ, Shimadzu Co.,Ltd). This test gives the strength evaluation and degradation degree of CFRTP after immersion test.

For bending test, span distance was 40 mm, and cross head speed was 2mm/min. Flexural strength σ (Pa) was determined using the following equation (Eq. 5):

$$\sigma = \frac{3Fl}{2bh^2} \quad (5)$$

Where, F is the maximum applied load (N), l is the span length (mm), b is the average sample width (mm), and h is the average thickness of sample (mm).

Moreover, retention of flexural strength (R) was determined using the following equation (Eq. 6):

$$R = \frac{\sigma(t)}{\sigma_0} \quad (6)$$

Where, $\sigma(t)$ is the flexural strength at time (t), and σ_0 is the flexural strength of the sample before immersion.

3.3.3 Cross section observation by Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)

After specific immersion time, sample was taken out and cut in half and the cross section were observed by SEM (JSM-3510LA, JOEL Co.,Ltd). The observation on the cross section is one of the method to determine the degradation degree of CFRTP. Furthermore, Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy was used to consider the penetration depth of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ion. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyzes elements by irradiating samples with electron beam, and detecting and analyzing X-rays generated on the samples. EDS measures the energy and intensity distribution of X-ray signal generated by the electron beam striking the surface. The elemental composition at point, along a line, or in a defined area can easily be determined.

3.3.4 Measurement of Electrical property (Electric conductivity)

The electrical conductivity shows the material's ability to conduct a corrosion current. With higher electrical conductivity, there will be more chance for galvanic corrosion to occur when attached to metals.

Volume electrical resistivity (inverse value of electrical conductivity) of the CFRTP specimens was measured by the 4-point probe method, using a direct current four point probe device (RG-5, NPS Co. Japan). The 4-point probe device was specified to have in-line fixed four probes made of Osmium alloy needles (diameter of 100 μm) containing in a brass body (FELL Type) [21]. A schematic diagram of the test circuit for measuring bar specimen resistivity by the 4-point probe method is presented in Figure 3. A direct current power source (PLE-120-0.6, Matsusada Precision Inc.) and voltmeter (MY-60, V&A instrument Co.,Ltd) were used for all measurements. The nominal radius of a probe tip was specified to be 100 μm . Equal probe spacing, s , was 1 mm and downward force was approximately of 0.2 kg [22]. A constant current, $I = 10$ mA (Ampere), was applied to the bar-shaped specimen through two outside probes with the help of a DC power source, and then the steady voltage across the other inside two

probes, V (Volt), was determined. According to the FPP (Four Point Probe) method theory [23,24], for a rectangular specimen of finite thickness, d (m), the resistivity, ρ (Ωm), is calculated as

$$\rho = \frac{\pi t}{\ln\left(\frac{\sinh(\frac{d}{s})}{\sinh(\frac{d}{2s})}\right)} \left(\frac{V}{I}\right) \quad (7)$$

However, when the test sample thickness is less than half the probe spacing ($d < s/2$), eq. 7 can be simplified as following,

$$\rho = \frac{\pi t}{\ln(2)} \left(\frac{V}{I}\right) \quad (6)$$

Here, the values of the volume electrical conductivity, θ , were obtained by inverting the corresponding values of the resistivity as follows,

$$\theta = \frac{1}{\rho} \quad (6)$$

The unit of electrical conductivity, σ , is S/m, where S (Siemens) is the inverse of the electrical resistance.

Figure 3 Schematic diagram of test circuit for measuring resistivity with the 4-point probe method.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Penetration and degradation behavior of CFRTP immersed in water and NaCl solution

4.1.1 Penetration behavior

Mass change have been measured to consider penetration mechanism of water and NaCl solution into CFRTP. In order to know the penetration type of water and NaCl solution followed the Fickian behavior or not, mass change was plotted in the term of square root of time ($t^{1/2}$). Mass change for all samples (No.1 - 6) after immersion in water at 80°C are shown in Figure 4(a). Also, Mass change for all samples (No.1 - 6) after immersion in 5% NaCl at 80°C are shown in Figure 4(b). In both Figure, a linear trend in the liquid absorption with root of immersion time was observed until the saturation point was reached, meaning that diffusion type of water and NaCl solution into all types CFRTP can be categorized following the Fickian diffusion theory.

The change of saturation mass (M_{∞}) compares to percentage of PA consist in CFRTP are shown in Figure 5. In spite of different immersion temperature, the saturation mass for the CFRTP with same PA66/CF ratio, are almost same, meaning that the saturation mass for CFRTP sample does not depend on the immersion temperature. However, amount of time to reach saturation is different due to

immersion temperature. At immersion temperature of 40°C, 60°C and 80°C, the time at saturation point are 625 hours, 144 hours, 49 hours respectively.

In both water and NaCl solution, the saturation mass increases proportionally to the amount of PA consist in the sample. From the predicted trend line, at PA:CF = 0:100 the saturation mass is zero, meaning that neither water nor NaCl solution depends on Carbon fiber content. In other word, water and NaCl solution can penetrates into the free volume of PA66, but not into Carbon fiber or the interface of PA and Carbon fibers.

Furthermore, according to the result of EDS, Cl⁻ was not found in the sample that was immersed for 2000 hours in water nor NaCl solution at 80°C, meaning that Cl⁻ cannot penetrate into CFRTP even in the case of long time immersion.

It can be concluded that, in both water immersion and NaCl solution immersion, only water can penetrates into the free volume of CFRTP.

Figure 4 Mass change of CFRTP at different time after immersion test (a) in water at 80 °C, (b) in 5% NaCl solution at 80 °C.

Figure 5 Saturation mass (M_{∞}) change comparing with percentage of PA consist in CFRTP after immersion test (a) in water, (b) in 5% NaCl solution.

4.1.2 Diffusion Coefficient

As previously mentioned, penetration of water and NaCl solution into CFRTP followed the Fickian diffusion law. Thus, diffusion coefficient can be determined from eq. 3. Using this approach, if $M(t)/M_{\infty}$ is plotted as a function of $t^{1/2}$, the diffusion coefficient can be obtained from the slope of the curve. The result of calculation is shown in Table 2. The result shows that, the diffusion coefficient is depends mostly on the immersion temperature.

In comparison between water and NaCl solution, the diffusion coefficient of the NaCl solution immersed samples is lower than samples in water immersion in all condition. This is due to the higher concentration of NaCl in solution that retard water diffusion by osmosis, which is also reported elsewhere [25,26].

Sample	Diffusion coefficient $D \times 10^{12}$ (unit: m^2/s)					
	Water			NaCl solution		
	40 °C	60 °C	80 °C	40 °C	60 °C	80 °C
1	1.069	5.301	10.905	0.938	4.842	10.236
2	1.521	5.505	13.874	1.361	5.202	13.126
3	1.486	5.330	13.911	1.275	5.162	13.580
4	1.521	5.723	14.192	1.387	5.492	13.708
5	1.454	5.611	14.213	1.289	5.083	14.048
6	1.567	5.865	14.432	1.495	4.886	14.112

Table 2: Diffusion Coefficient.

4.1.3 Degradation of CFRTP due to penetration of water and NaCl solution

When CFRTP contacted with water or NaCl solution, these environmental liquids penetrated into CFRTP sample and cause swelling, which increased volume but reduced the physical and mechanical properties of CFRTP. Flexural strength measurement were studied to confirm the decrease of mechanical properties and degradation of CFRTP. The result of three points bending test, in which comparison between flexural strength after and before penetration, so called retention of flexural strength are shown in Fig 6.

Figure 6 Retention of flexural strength of CFRTP at different time after immersion test in water at 80 °C (a.) Sample No.1 (CF:PA66 = 0:100), (b.) Sample No.5 (CF:PA66 = 40:60).

Initially, rapid decrease of flexural strength was observed inside the first 24 hours of immersion. The flexural for sample No.1 immersed in water and NaCl solution dropped down to 35% and 40% respectively. Also, the flexural for sample No.5 immersed in water and NaCl solution dropped down to 60% and 70% respectively. This is due to the plasticization by water. Then, the flexural strength was constant after 24 hours of penetration because plasticization by water is uniform after saturation was reached. Furthermore, after drying process the mass of all sample return to almost the same as before immersion and flexural strength was also recovered to almost 100%. This shows that, no chemical reaction or chain scission occurs by penetration of water or NaCl solution. The result for long time immersion also supported this conclusion. In a long run, after 2000 hours of water and NaCl solution immersion, the flexural strength dropped to the same value at the constant point and return to almost 100% after drying.

In comparison between water and NaCl solution, water incurred more effect on mechanical property of CFRTP than NaCl solution. This concluded that Na⁺ and Cl⁻ cannot penetrate into free volume of CFRTP. This complies with the result of electric conductivity measurement, that conductivity has not been detected at any immersion time.

4.2 Penetration and degradation behavior of CFRTP immersed in H₂SO₄ solution

Mass change and observation of degradation have been used to consider the behavior of H₂SO₄ solution. Mass change after immersion in 5% H₂SO₄ solution at 80°C was plotted in the term of square root of time ($t^{1/2}$) is shown in Figure 7. Also, for detection of SO₄²⁻ ion, penetration of sulfur element was observed using EDS analysis on cross-section. From the mass change profile and EDS analysis (Figure 10), the penetration behavior and degradation behavior can be separated into 3 zones.

4.2.1 Zone 1 – Water Diffusion Zone

In first zone, permeated water filled the free volume of the CFRTP until the saturation point is reached. The saturated mass of all sample at the end of zone 1 is almost the same as the saturation mass of water immersed sample shown in Figure 4, meaning that the diffusion rate of water is faster than that of sulfuric acid. Also, from EDS analysis, no distribution of S was found in this zone. It can be concluded that due to water diffusion, at the early period of immersion (0 hour – 36 hours), the diffusion of water as a solvent of sulfuric acid into CFRTP follows the Fickian type of diffusion.

The result of three points bending test, in which retention of flexural strength comparison (red line) with mass change (blue line) is shown in Figure 8. Initially (Zone 1), when CFRTP contacted with sulfuric acid solution, water penetrates into CFRTP sample and cause swelling, which increased volume but reduced the flexural strength of CFRTP. The flexural strength significantly decreased to 50%, in which the plasticization by water is uniform. At this point, no corrosion (chemical degeradation) has been incurred yet according to cross section observation by SEM (Figure 9(a))

4.2.2 Zone 2 – H₂SO₄ Diffusion + Surface Degradation Zone

In second zone, corrosion of surface area started to appear. This allows sulfuric acid (both H⁺ and SO₄²⁻) to penetrate into inner of CFRTP sample as shown in EDS analysis (Figure 10(b)), causing the mass to slightly increase until it reached peak at around 144 hour of immersion. It can be concluded that, after the degradation of surface, H⁺ and SO₄²⁻ separately diffused into sample causing a slight gain of mass (1%). The flexural strength was decreased gradually due to the starts of surface's degradation, which was observed by SEM (Figure 9(b)). At the end of this zone, the flexural strength decrease to about 30%.

4.2.3 Zone 3 – Inner Corrosion Zone

After the surface was totally degraded by sulfuric acid as observed from SEM (Figure 9(c)), the penetration rate of sulfuric acid increased significantly and fully penetrated into CFRTP after 400 hours (Figure 10(c)). This significant increase of sulfuric acid penetration caused the scission of PA66 chains in the CFRTP. The scissions of PA66 chains lost the physical property significantly. The decreasing of physical property (molecular weight) affected to a significantly decrease of mechanical property or flexural strength.

Furthermore, after a long immersion period (900 hours), as observation from SEM (Figure 9(d)) and EDS analysis (Figure 10(d)), the corrosion grows and propagates easily causing the sample to crack and eventual breakage.

4.2.4 Change of Electrical Conductivity

The electrical conductivity shows the material's ability to conduct an electric current. In this research, the measurement was conducted and the result (purple line) is shown in Figure 8 comparison with mass change (blue line). No conductivity has been induced in the first zone, in which only water penetrated into the sample. This complies with the result from water penetration behavior. However, in zone 2, in which sulfuric acid start to penetrate into the sample, electrical conductivity increase proportionally to the amount of H⁺ and SO₄²⁻ penetrated into the sample. Lastly, in zone 3, due to the significant increase rate of sulfuric acid penetration, electrical conductivity also increased rapidly.

As a result, it can be concluded that, H^+ and SO_4^{2-} can penetrate into CFRTP after the degradation of the surface start, which will induce a conductivity of CFRTP, and increase the chance for galvanic corrosion to occur when attached to metals.

Figure 7 Mass change of CFRTP at different time after immersion test in 5% H_2SO_4 solution at 80 °C.

Figure 8 Mass change (blue), Retention of flexural strength (red), and change of Electrical conductivity (purple) of CFRTP sample No.5 at different time after immersion test in 5% H_2SO_4 solution at 80 °C.

Figure 9 Cross section image taken by SEM after at different time after immersion test in 5% H_2SO_4 solution at 80 °C.

Figure 10 Sulfur element distribution at cross section of CFRTTP after immersion test in 5% H_2SO_4 solution at 80 °C.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Penetration behavior of electrolytic solution, such as water, NaCl and H₂SO₄ into polyamide based composite have been studied in this research. Furthermore, the degradation of CFRTP caused by the penetration have also been observed.

Penetration of water and NaCl solution into CFRTP can be categorized following the Fickian diffusion theory. Water and NaCl solution can penetrates into the free volume of PA66, but not into Carbon fiber or the interface of PA and Carbon fibers. Furthermore, according to the result of EDS, Cl⁻ particle cannot penetrate into CFRTP even in the case of long time immersion. It can be concluded that, in both water immersion and NaCl solution immersion, only water can penetrates into the free volume of CFRTP. This complies with the result of electric conductivity measurement, that conductivity has not been detected at any immersion time, due to the fact that Na⁺ and Cl⁻ cannot penetrate into CFRTP. From degradation observation, water was found to incur more decrease in flexural strength than NaCl solution. This complies with the result of diffusion coefficient, in which water has a higher value at all experiment condition. After drying process, flexural strength returned to almost 100% in both cases, concluded that there was no chemical reaction, such as chain scission.

Penetration behavior of H₂SO₄ solution and degradation of CFRTP can be separated into 3 zones; Zone 1: Water Diffusion, Zone 2: H₂SO₄ Diffusion + Surface Degradation Zone, and Zone 3: Inner Corrosion Zone. At the initial condition (Zone 1), due to water diffusion, the diffusion of sulfuric acid into CFRTP follows the Fickian type of diffusion. The flexural strength significantly decreased due to plasticization by water. In Zone 2, Hydrolysis reaction by sulfuric acid degraded the surface area, allows H⁺ and SO₄²⁻ ions to start penetrating through the surface. Lastly in zone 3, after the surface was fully degraded by H₂SO₄ solution, the penetration rate of sulfuric acid increased significantly. The scission of PA66 chains will cause CFRTP to crack and eventually break.

Furthermore, after degradation of surface occurred, electrical conductivity increase proportionally to the amount of H⁺ and SO₄²⁻ penetrated into the sample. Especially in zone 3 due to the significantly increased rate of sulfuric acid, electrical conductivity increased rapidly, which will increase the chance for galvanic corrosion to occur when CFRTP is attached to metals.

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